

Popular Article

Is Your Cat Finding Difficulty to Pee? Find This Useful

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Introduction

If your cat shows signs like straining while urinating, blood in the urine, passing urine frequently in less quantities, inappropriate urination, changes in behaviour either becoming aggressive or more docile, frequently vocalising, easily frightened and always grooming its perineal region, then probably it may be suffering from a condition called Feline Lower Urinary Tract Disease. This is nothing but your cat is having some problem in the urinary tract. It may be an infection, presence of stones, tumour, anatomical abnormalities or sometimes the cause is unknown. When the cause is unknown it is called as Feline Idiopathic Cystitis. If you're an owner of Persian or any other long-haired cat breeds like Birman, Laperm, Manx, Maine coon etc. beware that your cats are at increased risk of developing this condition. Siamese breed owners can calm down a bit as they are at reduced risk of developing it.

Why Does It Occur?

STRESS is the main reason for the cats to acquire FLUTD. This doesn't happen suddenly but it occurs over a period of time.

What Potential Stress Could I Cause to My Cat?

- ✚ Abrupt change in diet
- ✚ Restricting the access to outdoors
- ✚ Not maintaining the litter-box hygiene
- ✚ Loss of a family member
- ✚ Addition of a new family member
- ✚ Introducing a new pet
- ✚ Not paying attention to your cat
- ✚ If you're a multi-cat pet parent, separate litter boxes should be allotted to them
- ✚ Inter-cat conflict
- ✚ Changing to a new environment e.g., moving to a new house
- ✚ Feeding a dry diet
- ✚ Sedentary lifestyle
- ✚ Obesity
- ✚ Desexing your pets

Behavioural Changes

- Hides in dark place
- Easily panicked
- Becomes more sensitive to even normal sounds
- Aggression
- Loss of litter-box training

Scientific facts/ Rationale behind it:

Basically, cats will undergo several hormonal changes when the bladder is affected. The stress hormone "catecholamine" will be released continuously as a result of lack of negative feedback to the brain, hence the animal will be in a continuous state of fear. The protective layer integrity will be reduced in this state. When the protective layer lining the urinary bladder is disrupted by various causes, the noxious substance present in the urine gets a chance to permeate through the and contact with the pain neurons and causes

inflammation of the bladder. When the pain neurons are stimulated, it causes a release a substance which mediates pain.

Some cats are genetically predisposed i.e., if a kitten or a pregnant cat is exposed to stressful environment harsh enough to induce stress response, their central threat response system will be triggered which leads to enhanced sympathetic drive. This in turn disrupts the protective layer integrity leading to development of lower urinary tract disease.

Management - At pet parent's end:

Of all the FLUTD cases, 50-55% of the cases will fall into the category of Feline Idiopathic Cystitis. Because it is difficult to find the cause, it poses a great challenge to the veterinarians to treat this condition. Most of the feline idiopathic cystitis cases will resolve spontaneously within a few days irrespective of therapy, making response to treatment very hard to assess. Often what is considered to be improvement due to therapy is in fact a simple spontaneous recovery. Recurrence is one of the biggest nuisances in this condition. Of the clinical studies conducted with drugs, there is no significant benefit noticed. Reducing stress, particularly triggers of chronic stress, may help to reduce the recurrence and/or severity of the condition. To reduce the stress, we have to provide enriched environment. The primary treatment of the disease is long-term multimodal environmental modification while anti-anxiety drugs and nutritional supplements are recommended for chronic recurrent cases. Still, many medicines need to be evaluated for their efficacy and safety. The management that can be attempted at pet parent side is as follows:

Behavioural Therapy

Multimodal environmental modification (MEMO) or feline environmental enrichment (FEE), is defined as the addition of one or more factors to a relatively impoverished environment to the physical and psychological welfare of cats. It includes changes in management of litter boxes, food dishes, and water bowls.

Litter box:

To be optimally appealing to the cat, the litter box should be viewed as its own “plastic palace.” Place the litter in a well-ventilated area. It should be placed in an area free of intrusion by other pets and should not be placed in a high-traffic area or near appliances that may suddenly make noise and disturb the cat. The litter boxes of cats should be cleaned frequently.

We have something called litter box “rule of thumb”, it is called the “1+1” rule which means that you should have one more litter box than the number of cats you have. For e.g., if you have one cat, then provide with two litter boxes. This rule is formed to prevent your cat from peeing outside the litter box.

Food – Know your cat’s preferences:

The affected cats should be fed with moist food exclusively if accepted by the cat. The cat which is used to dry food may refuse eating moist food. During such instances, slowly introduce the moist food along with the food they are regularly provided. Even then if your cat refuse taking moist feed, you can try adding broth to the dry food or improve its water intake. Cats don’t prefer to eat and drink at the same place. So, it is advisable to keep their feed and water trough in different corners.

Water:

Unlike dogs, cats don’t drink much water. The main reason behind increasing the water intake is dilute the toxic substances in the urine. Avoid keeping the water in plastic containers; rather prefer ceramic or glass containers. Always fill the container with water up to the brim so that it is visible to the cat. Cats avoid drinking the water if they see their reflection in it. Moving waters attract them more to drink than still water. If possible, provide them with fountain water and dripping faucet.

Fountain water

Food dispensing toy

Play and Predatory Behaviour:

Encourage play and predatory behaviors of cats. Cats basically have their wild instincts of capturing and killing prey. But the indoor lifestyle in modern society has limited their activities and suppress their innate behaviors, which may predispose them to acquire stress-related conditions like FIC.

Food-dispensing toys can help mimic natural feeding behavior by encouraging a cat to work for its food

Feather Teaser toy

and explore its environment. Lasers points, feather teaser toy and several other toys are available commercially to engage your pets and relieve stress.

Establish sense of security:

Cats establish their boundaries by scratching and rubbing their bodies on objects. This gives them the sense of security and comfort. It is the responsibility of the cat parent, to allow them to express their chemical signals. Stable Scratching posts

can be provided to the cats next to its resting place. They tend to scratch when getting up after a period of rest.

Scratch Post

CLIMB POST

Cats should be offered plenty of space that enables them to express normal behaviours. It is therefore wise to offer several choices of high places for cats to climb and rest. In households with more than one cat, I believe it is essential that some of these structures should be sized for just one cat; this means that if one cat is already occupying a perch, it is more difficult for another individual to come and dislodge the occupant

Reference

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